

ISic3407

I.Sicily inscription 3407

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object

fragment

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tauromenium

Place of origin (modern)

Taormina

Provenance

contrada S. Leo, near the theatre

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Taormina, Antiquarium del
Teatro Antico (?), inventory 49

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140751

1. [— — — — — — — —]
2. [— — Ἴαν]ουαρίων
3. [— — ζήσα]ς ἔτη β.
- 4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644952

PHI 140751

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. *Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0437a (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)
undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.
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Ferrua, A 1989. Note e giunte alle iscrizioni cristiane antiche della Sicilia. Vatican. At no.482

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